

Some Common Misconceptions about

Findible **A**ccessible **I**nteroperable **R**eusable

- **FAIR is a clear-cut standard**
—its implementation varies on a case-by-case basis.
- **FAIR is equal to RDF, Linked Data, or the Semantic Web**
—it is their prerequisite.
- **FAIR is just about humans finding, accessing, and reusing data**
—it is primarily about machine-actionability.
- **FAIR only pertains to the Life Sciences**
—it applies to all digital objects across disciplines.
- **FAIR is equal to Open**
—it does not address ethical issues pertaining to the openness of data.

Remember!

"FAIR only speaks to the need to describe a process—mechanized or manual—for accessing discovered data, requiring clarity and transparency around the conditions of access and reuse."

go-fair.org. Accessed on 11 October 2024.

Find scholarly resources on the FAIR Principles in the EOSC SOA Group Library on Zotero.

